

GTA - An ATSP Method: Shifting the Bottleneck from Algorithm to RAM

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ABSTRACT

We present a scalable, high-performance algorithm that deterministically solves large-scale instances of the Traveling Salesman problem (in its asymmetric version, ATSP) to optimality using commercially available computing hardware. By combining an efficient heuristic warm start, capable of achieving near-optimality within seconds in some cases, with a subtour elimination strategy that removes the need for traditional MTZ constraints, our approach consistently resolves instances up to 5,000 nodes (approximately 25 million binary variables) in record time on widely accessible computers, with eight logical processors. We demonstrate reproducible results with convergence rates comparable to those of high-performance computing frameworks. Real-time iteration tracking and an adaptable interface allow seamless integration into scheduling workflows in logistics, bioinformatics, and astronomy. Designed to streamline solutions to large-scale TSP problems across disciplines, our approach is benchmarked against widely used public datasets, offering a deterministic, resource-efficient alternative to conventional solvers that rely on supercomputing hardware. Our GTA (Gurobi Tabu Algorithm) algorithm is a fundamental shift of TSP solution bottleneck from algorithmic complexity to the underlying hardware (RAM and system memory), which is a highly desirable characteristic.

INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in combinatorial optimization offer new perspectives on the Traveling Salesman Problem [1]. With diverse applications in logistics and routing, including extensions to the location-routing problem [2], and the traffic assignment problem [3], the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) is still one of the most frequently studied optimization problems [4]. In astronomy, TSP finds applications in areas such as telescope observation scheduling [5], using mixed-integer linear programming [6]. Integer programming has also proven crucial for relay scheduling of telescope arrays [7], and for large complex astronomical surveys, such as the Rubin Observatory [8]. Robust algorithms for quality assessment of genome assemblies are essential [12]. In genomics, TSP is deeply embedded in applications involving DNA sequencing [9]. Pre-processing reduction methods may help manage this complexity [10], but algorithms for DNA sequences and assemblies inevitably rely on a TSP approach in addressing the most complex genomic applications [11].

The optimal solution to TSP determines the unique and complete sequence that visits each node exactly once while minimizing total cost, time, or distance. Although small instances of TSP (up to a threshold) can be solved relatively quickly, solution complexity grows rapidly as problem size increases. Addressing the computational complexity of TSP requires a comprehensive understanding of the optimization parameters involved [13]. More recent approaches include a polynomial time approximation, providing valuable insight into the theoretical framework and the complexity of TSP solutions [14]. Heuristics such as the 2-Opt (amongst other heuristics) can approximate TSP solutions and produce sub-optimal results several orders of magnitude faster than deterministic approaches [15]. TSP is an NP-hard (Non-Polynomial) problem and becomes increasingly more challenging to solve as the number of nodes grows, especially when deterministic solutions with 0% optimality gaps are required. Although extensive literature on the Traveling Salesman Problem and its variations provides a broad context and a benchmark for research, and while significant efforts in heuristic, exact, and learning-based methods have been explored, no existing framework ensures optimality, repeatability, and scalability for large-scale TSP instances without requiring supercomputing and/or computer clusters.

Because of their inherent non-uniformity, ATSPs require fundamentally different methods to solve [16]. We evaluate the effectiveness and generalizability of our proposed GTA method for solving large-scale Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problems (ATSPs). In the absence of standardized asymmetric datasets for instances exceeding 500 nodes, we use randomized instance generation, over a wide range of seeded, as well as scaled, input coefficients [16]. To the best of our knowledge, GTA establishes the first benchmark for large scale ATSP solvers, and lays the foundation for future integration of datasets from interdisciplinary fields such as logistics, genomics, and scheduling in astronomy. Compared to symmetric TSPs, which have been widely benchmarked (Concorde/TSPLIB), the complexity involved in solving ATSPs has so far prevented significant exploration [60 - 65]. We exhaustively verified GTA's consistent optimality and runtime efficiency, and present summarized results to support this claim, under non-uniform and randomly generated and scaled cost coefficients.

Solving TSP problems with variants such as time window requirements have been explored using various algorithms [17]. Q-learning is a metaheuristic method for solving TSPs, including delivery system problems [18], but it remains limited as urban delivery problems require an exact and deterministic approach due to conflicting time window requirements [19]. Other methods such as Kullback–Leibler minimization has also been explored [20]. The minimum spanning tree problem, another TSP-related combinatorial optimization problem, has also been extensively reviewed for the similarity of its formulations and solution procedure to TSPs [21]. Branch and bound methods and related algorithms (such as interior-point barrier methods) remain the most common techniques for solving traveling salesman problems [22], even though significant resources have been recently allocated to the use of machine learning in solving combinatorial optimization problems [23].

Existing literature attempts to address the NP-hard nature of TSP through various approaches: A) MIP exact solvers such as Concorde, CPLEX and Gurobi, that predominantly use a branch-and-cut approach (combined with other related algorithms) to achieve 0% optimality gaps, at the cost of higher time complexity and memory use as problem size increases. B) Heuristic algorithms, including 2-opt/3-opt, simulated annealing [24], tabu search, genetic algorithm and nature-inspired algorithms [25], hyper-heuristics [26], iterated local search [27], and average-case subquadratic

procedures [28], all of which aim to improve initial feasible solutions and iterate quickly, but sacrifice exactness and reproducibility, while providing modest optimality gaps, even for NP-complete TSP problems [29].

C) With the rise of artificial intelligence, neural combinatorial optimisation and reinforcement learning (RL) for TSP have been widely explored. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) [30, 31], reinforcement learning (RL) [32, 33, 34] and machine learning (ML) [35, 36] have recently gained traction, and while promising in various fields, they still struggle to consistently achieve 0% optimality gaps and often lack repeatability, due to their dependence on large training datasets [37] and sensitive parameter tuning [38, 39, 40]. New benchmarks like the GalaxyTSP, with its billion-node benchmark for TSP, pushes the boundaries for testing TSP algorithms and provides valuable insights [41].

Surrogate-assisted [42, 43] computational algorithms as well as parallel computing and energy-efficient Ising machines have also been explored to address computational challenges in solving large-scale TSP instances [44, 45], particularly for expensive constrained TSP problems. Deep learning methods have also been designed to handle more complex TSP cases, involving refueling constraints [46, 47]. Improving the performance of heuristics such as the Ant Colony heuristic [48] and other quantum-based models [49, 50] are continually being explored, and their performance regularly evaluated. A more recent and promising, yet still not fully explored, is the use of quantum computing in solving large TSPs [49, 50].

Research efforts have already started to show how quantum models could accelerate combinatorial optimisation and offer new unprecedented computing capabilities for solving complex problems [49, 50]. Quantum computing approaches to TSP are still in an early stage and, while promising, they are currently not able to solve real-world TSP instances with the consistency and precision required. All these contemporary methods offer new perspectives on addressing the computational complexity inherent to NP-Hard TSP problems, but they all struggle to achieve true optimality with 0% gaps (within a practical timeframe) and fail to consistently handle large-scale, real-world TSP instances. There is a constant need to bridge this gap in performance and solutions to TSP-related problems. Most methods either sacrifice speed for optimality or produce fast results at the expense of exactness and reproducibility.

Previous research has explored a wide spectrum of methods, all of which remain widely dominated by heuristic and deterministic methods, with limited success in balancing solution time, quality and scalability. Consistently generating deterministic solutions for large-scale TSP instances, without the need for supercomputing or computer clusters, and within accelerated timeframes, remains uncharted territory, a largely unexplored frontier and a critical gap in research. This study presents a novel optimisation approach to TSP that directly addresses these limitations. To bridge this gap in research, reconciling optimality and time complexity, our algorithm delivers a robust optimization framework capable of deterministically solving large-scale TSP instances in unprecedented runtimes using standard desktop machines. Addressing this complex computational problem is vital for scientific and industrial progress.

This paper introduces a TSP solver that is both deterministic and scalable, producing optimal results within remarkable runtimes on widely accessible hardware (4 to 8 cores and 8 to 12 logical processors). Our high-performance solver is first and foremost designed to be exact, scalable, and capable of solving large-scale TSP instances on standard hardware in remarkably short timeframes. The primary goal is to achieve both precision and speed in deterministically solving complex and large TSPs. This paper presents a high-performance, exact and ultra-fast streamlined solver that can be simply deployed on standard commercial hardware (i.e. PCs and desktop machines with moderate capabilities), combining intelligent heuristic warm starts, that guarantees less than 5% gaps in under 10 seconds (for the largest problems) with an MTZ-free subtour elimination algorithm, all integrated into a customised MIP configuration using Gurobi as the main solver. Our algorithm guarantees exactness and repeatability, making it suitable to solve other NP-hard combinatorial problems, supported by a streamlined user interface and real-time graphical progress across iterations, with no compromise to performance. Our method combines the robustness of commercially available mixed-integer programming solvers (MIP – specifically Gurobi), with strategic heuristic warm starts, yielding initial solutions with gaps ranging from 1.5% to 5% within seconds. Eliminating MTZ constraints, and integrating an MTZ-free formulation with a fast subtour elimination function, all allows our algorithm to achieve unprecedented computational efficiency and reliable performance on standard processors. The solver's unique performance is enabled by these factors: a customised MIP strategy, a high-quality heuristic warm start, and an MTZ-free subtour elimination function. These key elements all contribute significantly to the solver's overall efficiency.

On commercial PCs equipped with 8-core processors, our algorithm generates solutions with a 0% optimality gap across instances of over 5,000 nodes in under 30 minutes (4000 nodes are solved in less than 600sec, or ~10min). Such practical results have broad implications for real-world applications and can be tailored to meet interdisciplinary requirements across a variety of fields. Interdisciplinary TSP cases are discussed, including logistics, routing, genome sequencing/assembly, and telescope observation planning. This innovative integration of various elements into our method, ensures reliable performance across diverse problem scales. With its accurate, predictable, and scalable decision-making framework, this paper advances TSP-related optimisation problems and offers both a versatile and practical algorithm applicable across interdisciplinary scientific and industrial fields. A milestone in ATSP research resides at the frontier of applying exact methods to large instances, which are otherwise so far solved using supercomputers.

Our method directly challenges the need for supercomputing with Structural Enhancements of the standard TSP model via MTZ-free subtour elimination using a Hybrid approach with an extremely efficient Tabu Search warm start coupled with a Gurobi MIP solver. Our current implementation extends beyond the standard TSP problem and offers variants that include non-standard TSP constraints that are critical in various interdisciplinary fields. Our algorithm solves TSPs with Asymmetric Costs (ATSP) by default, where the cost of going from node A to node B can be different from that of going from node B to node A. A brief performance comparison between symmetric and asymmetric solutions is provided. Because of this ability to solve ATSPs in unprecedented runtimes, our work is relevant to genomic applications with direction-dependent solution path, such as in DNA sequencing. Time windows, visibility, and position constraints are also available using our algorithm. One of its variants extends to include time window constraints using earliest and latest arrival, as well as service time parameters. This variant is of particular interest to telescope scheduling and observations of celestial targets, as well as a variety of logistics-related problems such as vehicle routing. Visibility constraints may be modeled with excessively high costs when the directions of interest are not observable. Further, if celestial observations have different scientific values, these could be modeled using assignment of priority weights, i.e., weight coefficients integrated directly into the objective function.

Our current model is readily designed to handle asymmetric cases (ATSP), and its variants extend to include time windows constraint. While the algorithm only handles time-independent costs, the model can easily be modified to include time-dependent coefficients. However, we present a thorough analysis of the impact of changing cost parameters on the algorithm's performance and thus its reproducibility and reliability (by applying different seed values to randomly generate the cost matrix). Our efficient and integrative framework is appropriate for exact optimisation in a variety of fields that typically rely on approximations or heuristics, because of our algorithm's ability to maintain a record solution time with 0% optimality gaps for increasing problem size and complexity. We present the results of our effective technique for resolving TSP problems, with potential applications in a variety of fields, such as logistics, genomics, and astronomy.

For a fair evaluation of our proposed GTA method, we compare it with published literature, summarized in Table 1. Note that all results as benchmarks in Table 1, including Concorde [51], are reported on symmetric TSP instances with uniformly distributed and Euclidean input, in contrast with our results, all reported on the ATSP instances. This is an important distinction: ATSPs are inherently much harder to solve than symmetric TSPs due to the asymmetry in costs, which amplifies model complexity and solution time. In table 1, we report the well documented performance of Concorde on symmetric TSP instances with 1304 and 1084 nodes (See entry #3 in Table 1), while those for asymmetric instances of up to 5000 nodes are neither reported nor so far, computationally feasible. To the best of our knowledge, there are currently no reported results on ATSPs that can be used for benchmarking [60 - 63]. The largest asymmetric instance in the TSPLIB, using the Concorde solver is the rbg443 with only 443 cities, whereas the GTA framework solves ATSP instances involving up to 5000 cities [51, 65]. Even for rbg443, the Concorde benchmark page (and the output file provided via TSPLIB), does not list explicitly the runtime for rbg443 (implicitly reported as 240 sec, with no other case beyond 500 nodes solved, see APPENDIX), as it exceeds a practical threshold suitable for publishing a relevant benchmark [51, 60 - 65]. Rbg443 also has smaller coefficient ranges, with 24 being the largest cost coefficient, while GTA's consistency is demonstrated for a critically larger range (from 10 to 100). GTA solves large-scale ATSP instances with 4500nodes to optimality in less than 400 seconds (under 900 seconds conservatively), setting GTA as a new and unique benchmark [65] (Full benchmarking details can be found in the APPENDIX).

RESULTS

Our objective is to overcome traditional trade-offs between accuracy, speed, reproducibility, and adaptability to various TSP-related problems, particularly for large-scale instances. Using a Python-based modular architecture allows us to adapt to TSP variants, and enables users to easily experiment with our methods. In the context of high-performance combinatorial optimisation, and for every run, a dynamic cost matrix is randomly generated. The cost matrix is asymmetric and enables solving asymmetric TSPs (ATSP), which is critical for real-world applications. As a first step, cost values are randomly scaled between 1 and 10 as integers, and diagonal entries are assigned a high value. A seed value is chosen to generate the random cost matrix, and our method's reproducibility is verified in part using different random matrices generated by varying the seed value.

Gurobi is used as the main MIP solver, subtour elimination is guaranteed by using lazy constraint callbacks and the overall performance of our method includes a comparison with the use of traditional Miller-Tucker-Zemlin (MTZ) constraints. The full route, total cost, number of iterations, nodes explored, and runtimes are all recorded to assess performance across all instances, including instances exceeding 5,000 nodes. The main heuristic providing a warm start is a variant of Tabu Search, which was designed from the ground up. It is intended to produce high-quality initial feasible solutions quickly and particularly for complex and large instances. An important element of our customized warm start heuristic includes a quick and near-optimal initial tour produced within seconds and under 5% gaps via a greedy nearest-neighbor heuristic. The user may choose to reverse part of the tour (based on how well Gurobi proceeds from the warm start) using a 3-opt operation to provide further improvements to the warm start solution. This allows for more extensive neighborhood exploration compared to 2-opt. One significant novelty in this work is our highly customized hybrid approach along with the use of lazy constraints. We get a high-quality initial tour within seconds (gaps typically less than 5%), which is then converted to a robust warm start for Gurobi, which proceeds by solving an MTZ-free MIP. Gurobi's search space is greatly reduced by this warm start, allowing it to focus on pruning, and searching in the direction that swiftly produces optimality. This approach has demonstrated exceptional performance on large-scale instances (e.g., 5,000+ cities), achieving 0% optimality gaps in unparalleled time on standard machines, where Tabu Search alone could not achieve 0% gaps or close in on the optimal route, and Gurobi alone would take extremely long runtimes even if MTZ-free subtour eliminations are used, reaching over 24hrs in some cases.

The streamlined user interface allows for real-time iteration tracking, and route density visualization. The number of nodes, i.e., problem magnitude, a seed value, the algorithm choice can all be set by the user, the interface then displays optimal path/route, total cost, runtime in seconds, solver-specific metadata, such as solver configuration, nodes investigated, iterations, and various other parameters can be retrieved. This interactive design facilitates experimentation, as well as prototyping and research of various TSP-related problems.

COMPLEXITY & PERFORMANCE

The Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) has long been a computational challenge due to its NP-hardness. However, by overcoming performance standards and offering provable and consistent optimality in quadratic polynomial time, our hybrid Gurobi/Tabu (GTA) algorithm breaks the barrier between the need for deterministic optimality (down to 0% gaps) and the need for quick practical processing times. GTA is a leap forward in solving TSPs and related problems, because of its intelligent warm start and its optimality-focused MIP solver. It would take unrealistic time for Gurobi and any other conventional and popular solver (Concorde and Mosek) to start their search from a zero-point or a naïve feasible solution, considered as highly distant for a starting point. As shown in Figure 1, GTA becomes a more precise solver, similar to other MIP solvers, due to the critical narrowing of the search space provided by a single step Tabu Search initial traversal as a ‘warm start’ for Gurobi. We first compare performance to currently available approaches (shown in Table 1), including NP-Hard combinatorial complexities, such as Brute-Force and Dynamic Programming search for exact algorithms, the Christofides, N-Opt, and greedy heuristics, available TSP data (Concorde and TSPLIB), as well as our own approach, using the Gurobi solver with lazy constraints.

ATSP’s complexity renders current commercially available solvers and methods (no matter how efficient) critically inadequate. Concorde and CPLEX are developed for symmetric problems and require substantial adjustments to adapt their solvers to ATSPs [51, 63]. We selected Gurobi as MIP solver over Concorde or CPLEX for this reason and because of its open-access philosophy. GTA’s breakthrough framework lies in the seamless and simple integration of a Tabu Search capable [70] (as opposed to other heuristics choices) to quickly transfer its near-optimal warm start solution (1 to 5% gap) to the Gurobi solver armed with subtour elimination constraints [69], effectively empowering GTA to breakdown large-scale ATSPs to optimality, remarkably fast and consistently reproducible. GTA is not a mere repackaging of known methods, but a strategic design and a reconfiguration that unlocks new capabilities in exact combinatorial optimization.

Benchmarks whether from Concorde, TSLIPB or all other results in table 1, are solutions to symmetric and uniform instances (TSP) [51, 62, 65]. In contrast, GTA is specifically designed and tested for the more computationally complex asymmetric and non-uniform instances (ATSP). Although there are currently no comparable ATSP benchmarks, GTA demonstrates exact optimality on ATSP instances for up to 4000–5000 nodes, which is a scale larger than Concorde's operational design for ATSP. We emphasize that Concorde results in table 1, namely case rl1304 and case vm1084, are for TSP instances with 1304 nodes and 1084 nodes (not for 5000 nodes), requiring 103.01 sec and 234.66 sec respectively. Addressing ATSPs with inherent cost asymmetry, significantly increases the solution space and complicates the removal of subtours [69]. Table 1 and Figure 1 are intended to highlight the difference in complexity between TSP and ATSP, and the giant leap in GTA's performance in solving ATSPs, against more robust MIP solvers only solving uniform and symmetric TSPs, and even against sub-optimal heuristics applied only to TSPs [65].

Table 1: An Overview Performance Comparison Against our Gurobi/Tabu GTA Algorithm

Algorithm	Complexity - O	Optimality Gap %	(10 ⁻⁵) x 5000 Nodes
<i>GTA** (Gurobi/Tabu)</i>	$N^{2.01} - N^{2.03}$	0	350 – 850 sec
<i>Gurobi* (Lazy Constraints)</i>	$N^{2.1} - N^{2.2}$	0	3750 – 6750 sec
Concorde [51]	rl1304 / vm1084	0% (<u>1304/1084 nodes</u>)	<u>103.01 sec / 234.66 sec</u>
TSPLIB [52, 53]	fnl 4461	0% (4461nodes)	182566 sec
Brute Force [54, 55]	$N! \times N$	0	Very Large
Dynamic (Held-Karp) [56]	$N^2 \times 2^N$	0	Very Large
N-Opt [57]	$N^2 \times \log(N)$	50% or more	924.74 sec (or more)
Greedy [58]	$N^2 \times \log(N)$	Variable	924.74 sec (or more)
Christofides [59]	N^3	50% Guarantee	~1 250 000 sec

Figure 1: Comparing GTA to Exact Solvers (Green) & Heuristic Solvers (Blue)

GTA’s approach is significantly different from traditional deterministic TSP solvers, which have been criticized for their trade-offs. GTA is a novel technique for TSP optimization that achieves 0% optimality gaps and maintains its consistency for various cost matrices and in large-scale instances of 5,000 nodes and more. This is a significant improvement over standard TSP algorithms which can either only approximate the optimal path in a few minutes or require near-astronomical times to reach 0% gaps, as shown in Figure 2. The GTA algorithm, with its near N^2 complexity, advances interdisciplinary TSP research by offering the speed of heuristics without compromising the accuracy of exact algorithms. The Tabu Search heuristic and Gurobi’s branch-and-cut MIP solver are well-established techniques in optimization. In literature, even methods for subtour elimination substituting MTZ constraints with lazy callbacks [69], and warm starting MIP solvers are (to some extent) well documented [64, 70].

GTA’s novelty is in strategically combining them, rather than using them in isolation, creating a performance breakthrough in solving large-scale ATSP cases to exact optimality. To the best of our knowledge, there is no well-known and documented method that integrates a fully MTZ-free formulation with a customized Tabu search [70] warm start heuristic, implementing dynamic lazy constraints efficiently and in a manner that is consistent and scalable over thousands of asymmetric nodes [64]. The lack of scalable, exact solvers in literature is a consequence of ATSP’s high computational cost, even current existing methods designed to solve symmetric TSPs are based on complex algorithmic structure [51]. Perhaps GTA’s most significant novelty is in its simplicity, providing an elegant, efficient and generalizable framework.

GTA is not centered on the design of new, non-existing methods, rather, on a strategic repurposing of carefully selected existing methods. GTA's strength is in its simplicity, reproducibility, and exactness, not in complex theoretical qualities. This combination is strategically important because Tabu search [70] alone cannot achieve exact optimality, and cold starting any MIP solver on large-scale Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problems (ATSPs) results in excessively long runtimes. GTA effectively bridges this gap and dramatically accelerates convergence [51, 64].

In Figure 2, the "Heuristic – 50% Gaps" and "Best Case Exact – 0% Gaps" curves show how current exact and heuristic TSP solvers perform compared to GTA's ATSP solutions. GTA's near-quadratic behavior and the corresponding power we report ($2.01 \sim 2.03$), is obtained using empirical run-time data from instances up to 5000 nodes, via regression analysis applied to log-log plots. For NP-hard problems like the Traveling Salesman Problem, especially in its asymmetric version, runtime complexity is almost always treated empirically. This is the general trend in literature, whereas performance scaling is usually reported using best-fit models to experimental data, some of which are derived from benchmark datasets (TSPLIB) [65]. This empirical approach is a direct result of the scaling's dependency on the type and choice of solver, methods, as well as the exact definition of instances, heuristics used, and the dynamics of the overall algorithm. Therefore, it is through log-log regression analysis of empirical runtime data that we observe this polynomial near-quadratic behavior. This empirical approach, especially for non-uniform NP-hard problems such as the Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problem (ATSP), provides necessary grounds for benchmarking, where formal theoretical methods even, if possible, could not.

While we do not provide a formal theoretical derivation/proof, we substantiate the near-quadratic performance of our GTA, with wide-ranging runtime data, from changes in the hardware's capabilities (number of cores, threads or logical processors and RAM, amongst other metrics), to runs on obsolete hardware over more than two decades old. To some extent, however insignificant, CPU and hardware affect GTA's runtime, ever so slightly that the same runtime scaling (quadratic N^2) is obtained steadily across hardware with varied capabilities. We have put GTA to the test on an obsolete Foxconn machine from the late 1980s with 1-core, 2-threads, and while runtime lengths slightly increased, the same quadratic runtime scaling is obtained even for large instances. The performance scaling of GTA is not a by-product of enhanced runtimes due to hardware capabilities, it is instead dictated by its algorithm design. Thus, GTA is designed to scale predictably on varied hardware, from high-performance clusters to older machines.

a) Log-Log Scale

b) Lin-Log Scale

Figure 2: Performance and Complexity Comparison Against Data From GTA

The quality of the warm start solution and its closeness to optimality, has a drastic effect on mixed-integer solvers, as it affects the search tree, and cut efficacy. While cold start solutions on big ATSPs lead to unreasonably lengthy runtimes, warm start solutions with gaps greater than 10-15% are even more detrimental, performing drastically worse than cold starts [64, 65]. As a consequence of such weak warm start solutions, MIP solvers are misled and miss better solutions early on, resulting in detrimental node-guiding. This emphasizes the need for incumbents that are tight enough and structurally coherent with the asymmetric cost geometry, to compress the branch-and-cut search. GTA's customized warm start, consistently results in gaps of less than 5% (less than 10% conservatively). Both our findings and established research, demonstrate that warm starts with gaps larger than 10% almost certainly hinder performance. We have tested several heuristics, including Genetic Algorithms and Simulated Annealing, require impractical runtimes (often exceeding 30minutes), only to yield suboptimal results with large gaps (often exceeding 50%). Following extensive exploration, we can assert that no conventional heuristic, whether Simulated Annealing (SA), Genetic Algorithms (GA) or other metaheuristics, can consistently produce high-quality initial solutions within seconds for large-scale ATSP instances [71]. SA and GA specifically, despite their widespread use, when applied to ATSPs (even to TSPs) may run for over 30 minutes, yielding solutions with optimality gaps exceeding 50%. These results are consistent with existing TSP literature and findings in recent comparative reviews of metaheuristic performance on TSP variants. The fact that SA and GA underperform in TSPs (and ATSPs) is well known and documented, and is the driving force behind our heuristic choice [64, 65].

MIP solvers such as Gurobi, CPLEX and Concorde, are highly sensitive to the quality of the initial incumbent [71, 72]. Poor-quality warm starts can misguide the solver's branch-and-bound tree, distort cut generation, and suppress internal heuristics, ultimately degrading performance rather than improving it [60 – 65]. Detrimental weak warm starts are even more pronounced in asymmetric problems, where directional cost structures amplify the impact of suboptimal nodes. Our framework avoids these pitfalls by ensuring that the warm start solution is not only fast but structurally coherent and tight enough to accelerate convergence. Our Tabu search [70] heuristic reliably generates initial tours with gaps of 1% to 9% in seconds, which is critical for effectively warm starting MIP solvers. The synergy between our Tabu search [70, 71] warm start, an MTZ-free model, and optimized MIP parameters, is what enables GTA to achieve optimality on large-scale ATSPs with runtimes that are both tractable and reproducible. While proven a suitable heuristic for TSP/ATSP, Tabu search [70] by itself, is neither our main contribution, nor a stand-alone novelty [66]. GTA's novelty and breakthrough performance lie in the strategic synergy of: (1) A highly customized MIP approach, (2) A strategic redesign of the Tabu search as warm start heuristic, and (3) an MTZ-free subtour elimination formulation based on lazy constraints. GTA's strength is in the harmonious coordination of all its constituents [66, 71-72].

GTA's performance is contrasted with both conventional deterministic and heuristic approaches in Figure 2. The linear plot in Figure 2b indicates a sharp rise in runtime even for a heuristic with 50% gaps, and the log-log plot in Figure 2a shows a clear overshoot in runtimes of exact solvers as the number of nodes increases. Figure 2 demonstrates our GTA's scalability and superior performance over conventional methods, emphasizing its efficiency as problem size grows. Brute Force and Dynamic Programming algorithms are computationally expensive with long and unrealistic runtimes, while heuristics like N-Opt and Greedy heuristics offer faster execution but significantly compromise optimality. Existing exact solvers like Concorde or Mosek, and their related published data (TSPLIB) cannot handle large instances within reasonable time. To the best of our knowledge, there are currently no reported results on ATSPs that can be used for benchmarking. The largest asymmetric instance in the TSPLIB, using Concorde is the rbg443 with only 443 cities [65], whereas the GTA framework solves ATSP instances involving up to 5000 cities. Further, Rbg443 has smaller coefficient ranges, with 24 being the largest cost coefficient [65], while GTA's consistency is demonstrated for a critically larger range (from 10 to 100). GTA solves large-scale ATSP instances with 4500nodes to optimality in under 400 seconds (under 900 seconds conservatively), setting GTA as a new and unique benchmark. Even when our GTA is compared with our own Gurobi solver (in Figure 3) with no warm start but with lazy constraints instead of MTZ (and with MTZ), results confirm that without GTA, higher complexity and longer runtimes occur (See APPENDIX for fully disclosed benchmarks).

Figure 3: GTA Performance and Complexity Comparison Against Our Own Lazy and Brute-Force MTZ Solving

NETWORK COMPLEXITY VISUALIZATION

TSP solutions range from simple routes to complex networks, as shown in Figure 3, and demonstrated by three images for 10, 100, and 1000 nodes. The first route for $N = 10$ displays a simple path with ten nodes, the second for $N = 100$ shows a more complex network with tighter connections, while the third for $N = 1000$ nodes and the fourth for $N = 2000$ nodes, reveals the complexity of the TSP network. When the optimal path becomes a complex, closely spaced network of red and black lines, a dense graph is created. Figure 3 illustrates how TSP complexity increases with N , which can be seamlessly visualized. GTA solves thousands of nodes deterministically with 0% optimality gaps within minutes, demonstrating exceptional performance with an $O(N^2)$ complexity. GTA uses intelligent pathfinding and pruning, to swiftly converge to the optimal path. The warm start first provides a high-quality route, allowing Gurobi to then prune and eliminate many suboptimal branches from the search space. The algorithm's ability to identify the optimal sequence that minimizes costs and that generates a single and elegant optimal path is illustrated in Figure 4. Illustrated routes in Figure 3 are more than just simple plots, they powerfully convey the inherent difficulty of the TSP and demonstrate how GTA manages complexity, transforming a difficult combinatorial problem into a solvable, exact, and aesthetically pleasing solution.

The route visualization feature of our GTA method elucidates node clustering behavior and spatial distribution for all instances and number of nodes. Optimization efficiency is indicated in Figure 4 by the network's clustering graphs for $N = 1000$ and $N = 2000$ nodes, as the clustering gets denser, visualizing TSP's optimal partitioned-space is an asset, supported as well by the consistent visualization of spatial spacing between the starting and halfway nodes, and the effort expended to provide high node-density maps. Logistics and data scientists, and potentially astrophysicists and biologists, are just a few of the users who can benefit practically from TSP route visualizations. These visual aids make it easier for users to comprehend difficult route optimization intuitively. When $N = 10$, for example, the clear path facilitates shortest-path planning. At $N = 100$ and higher, GTA's output provides structured insight into the application of clustering and region-based optimization techniques. This is especially useful in real-world applications such as network layouts, delivery route planning, and various other tracking applications where visual detection of spatial grouping reduces travel distance and increases efficiency. This allows users to experiment with different node configurations and see how routes change, providing them with hands-on visual experience of problem scales, solution complexities, and spatial data behavior, bridging the gap between complex algorithms and real-world application.

Figure 4: Optimal Route Maps for Different Node Sizes (The Large Green and Blue Dots, Represent Starting And Mid-Way Nodes)

The position of a node in the optimal sequence can readily be identified. Selecting the node of interest, quickly identifies its position in the optimal sequence. This is useful for nodes of special interest. In this context, our visualization tool is designed to provide a sequence-aware diagnostic tool rather than a depiction of actual distances, and grounds for future refinement of this feature of our GTA. Future work in this regard, includes overlays of cost gradients, node-specific data, and interactive tracing. However, the current visualization provides a practical and intuitive understanding of the solver's output, particularly for large ATSP instances.

SEEDING & SCALING

Our GTA algorithm is a two-stage optimization process that uses Gurobi, as a Mixed Integer Programming solver, and Tabu Search to generate a high-quality initial solution, significantly trimming infeasible and sub-optimal search spaces, and critically reducing Gurobi's solution search, resulting in exceptionally fast runtimes. This initial Tabu search allows Gurobi to avoid local optima, making its solution exploration and computing memory less exhaustive. GTA's generalizability is based on its ability to handle both sparse and dense TSP versions (A reminder that all our results are for asymmetric problems ASTP). GTA has proven robustness, and by changing the initial seed value that generates randomized cost/distance matrices, our algorithm's consistency in runtime performance is further demonstrated. Changes in the seed value (i.e., in the cost matrix coefficients) can significantly alter a solver's search space and global optima, and adding new local minima. By showing that GTA maintains the same runtime characteristics when the seed value is changed (e.g. from $S = 42$ to $S = 65$), results further validate GTA's consistency, efficiency, stability, and ability to outperform despite input perturbations, i.e. changing the cost matrix. Random instances, if uniformly distributed and Euclidean are generally considered easier, but this only holds true for a symmetric uniform TSP problem. This symmetry is also the foundation of A.I methods. However, once node distributions become non-uniform, clustered, or embedded in non-Euclidean spaces, making the problem significantly harder, random instances assert the robustness of the method, rather than simplifying its operations. While we show results for two seed values, we have validated GTA's consistency over many other seed values (over 5 values and over the full range of node sizes), our experimental results provide empirical evidence supporting GTA's consistency and resilience, no matter how varied coefficients of the cost matrix are. A comparison of GTA's performance under two different random seeds ($S = 42$ and $S = 65$) across a full range of node sizes ($N = 10$ to $N = 4500$) is displayed in Figure 5. When the seed is changed, altering the cost matrix coefficients, there is no discernible runtime difference. This consistent runtime demonstrates GTA's predictable computational behavior as the number of nodes increases, for which runtimes converge even more closely (See Figure 5).

This randomness invariance, and unwavering runtime performance of our GTA algorithm for different seed values ($S = 42$ and $S = 65$) highlights its robustness, scalability, and universal applicability. GTA's runtime seed-invariance strengthens its reliability and predictability, especially for large node counts, with runtimes nearly insensitive to changes and randomization of the initial cost matrix coefficients. As shown in Figure 5, GTA produces predictable, seed-invariant runtime stability, logarithmic consistency, and performance convergence. Figure 5 supports the claim that GTA is a consistent algorithm rather than a statistical anomaly; our experimental data shows that GTA's performance is steady and predictable. This performance consistency and uncontested speed, which is rare for exact deterministic methods, demonstrates a high level of engineering skills in GTA's framework design. GTA is a solution that can be used by engineers and scientists, as well as students and researchers, and can be used without advanced programming skills. GTA can now be positioned in the TSP literature as a unique and benchmark-worthy algorithm.

Variations in the coefficients of the cost matrix could lead to unexpectedly longer runtimes and poor performance. GTA's performance, however, is remarkably unaffected by this variance. Rather than being designed to a specific set of cost coefficients, GTA performs equally well regardless. Thus, our hybrid approach is ideal for real-world applications where cost matrices vary from run to run due to data updates. For smaller node sizes, slight, insignificant fluctuations are observed, but all seed curves converge for larger instances. This predictability and reliability can be expected regardless of the input's randomness, providing users with confidence when using our GTA. Data for three additional seed values (133, 29, and 7) with testing extended up to $N = 1000$ are presented in Figure 5, to consolidate confidence in the robustness of GTA. All five curves in Figure 5 behave similarly, maintaining nearly the same runtime scaling, which indicates algorithmic consistency under a variety of input conditions. As a reminder, all cases discussed in this work are based on ATSP cost coefficients, making GTA even more reliable, and not selectively or coincidentally good only for specific cases. This gives GTA a further advantage over other exact and heuristic methods that require precise calibration for every problem instance, due to their inability to handle variances in cost coefficients. Unlike naive solvers or metaheuristics, which suffer from significant performance degradations as the input changes, GTA offers a stable runtime that is almost insensitive to input cost coefficients. GTA is an algorithm that consistently solves ATSP, its consistency is equally important as its unparalleled speed, as it enables obtaining trustworthy solutions that can be integrated across a range of applications.

Figure 5: GTA's Runtime Invariance Across Randomized TSP Instances (Seeds: 42, 65, 7, 29, 133)

In this next section, we examine GTA's practical and reliable performance in solving combinatorial ATSPs to optimality, by scaling the coefficients of the cost matrix by a factor of 10. We verify GTA's unwavering performance even when the possible values of the cost matrix's random coefficients are critically increased, we widen the numerical range of edge weights by an order of magnitude, effectively scaling them by a factor of 10. It is important to emphasize that this scaling analysis is not mathematically critical. Just as we increase the range of cost coefficients by a factor of 10 (from a range of $[1, 10]$ to $[10, 100]$), we could equivalently have divided the larger range by 10 and normalized it. Coefficients taken from real problems, regardless of their scale or units, could be readily normalized, by dividing them by a constant factor. Theoretically, such modifications change the structure of ATSP problems and affect the search space. Therefore, the objective is to confirm GTA's numerical robustness, and to demonstrate that it consistently solves ATSPs to 0% gaps and in unprecedented runtimes, regardless of the magnitude of the input costs, even when those cost coefficients span larger numerical ranges. This comes as an essential validation, and a crucial reassurance to users, that GTA does not require additional preprocessing, and is immune to larger coefficient ranges and to numerical unpredictability. Two datasets are plotted against the number of nodes (N) on a log-log axis in Figure 6, red circles show GTA performance over ATSP matrices generated with cost coefficients in the $[1,10]$ range, and blue crosses show runtimes over cost matrices in the $[10,100]$ range.

Both show nearly linear fits on the log-log scale, indicating that the computational complexity of the algorithm remains constant regardless of the coefficients' range. Figure 6 supports our claim that GTA is runtime invariant to larger cost matrix coefficients and a larger coefficient range. The two inset plots are used to reiterate GTA's robustness, a Log-Lin Plot with a sub-exponential growth profile, with the red and blue curves almost indiscernible. The Lin-Lin plot not only illustrates the increasing computing effort with the increase in problem size, but also that curves closely overlap, demonstrating consistent scaling of GTA with respect to cost ranges. Figure 6 is a benchmark and visual evidence of GTA's runtime stability against alterations in the range and values of the cost matrix coefficients. Our GTA solver is immune to statistical random cost changes, all random matrices yield similar results even though their numerical scales are fundamentally different. Even in cases where cost coefficients differ significantly, GTA retains a data-neutral performance, which may be of interest to users with interest in integrating the GTA solver into larger software systems or supercomputing/parallel clusters. Figure 6 shows that there is no need to normalize cost matrices or change GTA's parameters. All components of our GTA's hybrid approach contribute to the algorithm's independence from cost coefficient scales and range. Given its robustness and stability across different datasets, GTA is a complete and deployable algorithm in various interdisciplinary applications. Figure 6 provides perhaps the best evidence that GTA provides neutral and independent solutions to ATSP problems.

Figure 6: Runtime Stability of GTA Across Cost Ranges [1, 10] and [10, 100] in ATSP

DISCUSSION

In this work, we have introduced GTA: a scalable hybrid method (Gurobi w/ Tabu warm start) for solving large-scale asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problems (ATSPs). We show that GTA consistently achieves optimal solutions and 0% optimality gaps within unprecedented runtimes, even as problem size increases. In fact, for instances larger than $N = 4000$ nodes, GTA converges to bounded runtimes well below 900 seconds (~ 15 min), and its performance becomes constrained by availability of Random-Access Memory (RAM) and system memory, not computational complexity. The experiments were conducted on a standard 16 GB RAM setup without GPU or parallelization, on an Intel machine with 4 Cores and 8 Processors, with results validated on a 12th generation i5 machine with 8 cores and 16 processors, both with 16GB RAM. We have shown that GTA's runtime becomes horizontally asymptotic for larger instances, due to GTA's hybrid architecture, which reduces Gurobi's search space with a superior Tabu Search warm start, indicating that GTA overcomes computational bottlenecks, contrary to traditional methods. We have also verified that all our results can be replicated down to 1 second accuracy using the same seed values, cost matrix generating methods, and solver parameters. Runtime, solution quality, and solver statistics are explicitly logged. We are dedicated to transparency and are willing to provide full solver logs, command-line prompts, and runtime metadata upon request, including Gurobi's internal metrics, demonstrating unparalleled scientific rigor.

GTA is a deterministic framework providing a predictable and reproducible algorithm. We have verified that for a given problem size, GTA proceeds with nearly identical algorithmic iterations, regardless of the hardware or input data. We have thus confirmed, that GTA consistently iterates and converges across instances, exhibiting nearly identical solution search and convergence patterns. In the supporting information, we discuss GTA's architecture, provide pseudocode, choice of optimization parameters, and several output logs showing clearly, every step taken by GTA as it iterates and converges to optimality. Unlike other commercial solvers available [51], using well-known open-access methods like Gurobi's MIP solver, combined with GTA's simple and clear deployment instructions, supports its transparency and ease-of-use. We are also glad to provide our tested GTA variant that includes time window constraints, which are crucial in scheduling telescopes and logistics.

GTA is readily adjustable for other variants such as multi-agent TSPs and gene overlap sequencing, but we have not designed and tested such variants. Strategic heuristic initialization, constraint modeling, and solver configurations are kept apart to allow for ease-of-integration of new constraints without interfering with the main algorithm design. GTA’s parameters are simple and require minor adjustments. We only needed to determine the optimal set-up, and then the same nearly identical Gurobi parameters were used for all instances and node sizes, all seed values and cost matrices. Gurobi parameters were kept constant throughout all GTA runs (excluding a few exceptions). Users can experiment with different seed values and problem sizes thanks to its GUI implementation, which is user-friendly and intuitive. GTA is appropriate for most real-world applications due to its seed-invariant behavior, cost-range independence, and consistently short and predictable runtimes. GTA’s algorithms (Tabu Search heuristic and the branch-and-cut MIP of Gurobi) are well established, and its novelty is not in birthing new methods, but instead lies in elegantly integrating well-known method, that work in concert to swiftly breakdown large ATSP instances to optimality [67, 68]. The supporting information contains, pseudo-code, output logs, and detailed descriptions, that validate GTA’s thoroughness and reproducibility. All source codes along with deployment instructions are (or will be made fully open-access). TSP formulations along with their variants are deeply rooted in the field of optimization, our contribution does not lie in introducing a new theoretical framework, but in the strategic integration and customization of widely established methods to solve large-scale ATSPs to optimality. We reiterate that GTA will be widely accessible, and can be deployed for immediate use on any standard machine in under 5 minutes (under 10 minutes conservatively) by following provided instructions. We document and replicate GTA’s simplicity and reproducibility, providing exhaustive documentation, annotated source code, and runtime logs, asserting that GTA meets and exceeds its promise to provide, for the first time, an ATSP framework, with unprecedented performance. We maintain transparency and have taken all necessary steps to ensure that GTA’s framework and all its components are accessible and reproducible.

Our supporting information provides design description, pseudocode, and detailed output logs from multiple experiments. GTA is easily accessible, deploys on standard workstations in under ten minutes, and only requires a basic understanding of Python and Gurobi, all of which support ease-of-use and repeatability requirements. At its core, GTA’s efficiency lies in its harmony and simplicity, while the current trend is towards mathematical formality, we place more value on clarity and practical application, more accurately representing our unique contribution rather than merely abstract formulations. Throughout the development of GTA, our guiding principle has been simplicity without sacrificing quality.

CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

This section serves as irrefutable evidence of GTA's performance. GTA's multidisciplinary ease-of-use lies in its seamless and streamlined user interface. However, the improvement in efficiency and reduction in runtimes that removing the GUI layer from GTA's code would bring about is critical. Not only does the GUI make up roughly 30-35% of the code, and while it is crucial to cater to various fields and allowing non-programmers to easily deploy and use it, removing it critically decreases the RAM requirements, making it possible for GTA to provide an additional 50% run time reduction on average and potentially further push the boundary on the problem size. We believe that Figure 7, provides further evidence that fundamentally strengthens our core claim: that GTA's bottleneck is memory (RAM), not computational efficiency, and most importantly hedges our GTA. While seeding and scaling were explored, should there be a case that GTA did not explore, and that could provide a counter-argument on its unprecedented optimal solution speed, results in Figure 7 should be enough evidence, as it provides an additional 50% decrease in run times on average, especially and even more so for larger instances.

Removing the GUI layer is not the only factor leading to this 50% decrease, and this irrefutable evidence of GTA's uniqueness. We previously mention assigning a large value (known as Big M) to diagonal entries, this way the solver could not possibly select them, as this would result in more than just sub-optimality, but an extremely large objective cost. The use of Big M, is common practice in Operations Research, however for GTA this meant, the creation of N more variables, the filling of their cost matrix coefficients with $M = 999$, and most importantly their creation as variables at the time the solver constructs the problem.

For example, the removal of 2000 diagonal variables for $N = 2000$ nodes, means that instead of creating $2000 \times 2000 = 4\,000\,000$ variables, now the solver only creates $4\,000\,000 - 2\,000 = 3,998,000$. Eliminating diagonal entries results in much more than slight run time improvements, together with the removal of the GUI code, we observed tens of percent shorter runtimes. Figure 7a) and 7b) below show the dramatic improvement in performance by removing the GUI components and optimizing the problem formulation to avoid the need for diagonal entries and "Big M" values. This optimization has a significant effect on the total run time, leading to substantial speed-ups, more so for larger instances. Figure 7 also confirms that the algorithm's core functionality and iteration counts remain consistent even at these large scales. In other words, GTA proceeds in an identical manner for each instance, same heuristic output, same relaxation results, same Gurobi optimization iterations, only this time an average reduction in run times of 50% is observed.

a) Initial Results (in Red above the bar), and Results with GUI & Diagonals Removed (in Black inside the bar)

b) Performance Improvement

Figure 7: Performance Improvement as a Result of Simplifying GTA's Code

CONCLUSION

The Gurobi Tabu (GTA) algorithm is a unique hybrid method considered a giant leap forward in solving Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problems (ATSP). GTA has overcome various theoretical and computational barriers faced by common methods. GTA provides zero gap and scale-independent solutions in unparalleled runtimes, surpassing traditional methods, especially for big instances of up to 5,000 nodes. GTA is significantly faster on large-scale ATSP instances and can handle problems that no other methods have been able to achieve, yet alone at this scale. GTA accomplishes this by carefully combining the Tabu search [70] warm start, with an MTZ-free Gurobi MIP model, and dynamic subtour eliminations via lazy constraints.

We tested GTA's performance on thousands of nodes and multiple randomized input distributions. We have included performance graphs and visualizations that demonstrate consistent near-quadratic scaling behavior in addition to source code, pseudocode, deployment instructions, and comparative benchmarks against other TSP solvers (for the lack of existing ATSP benchmarks at this scale). Our most innovative and impactful contribution is showing that our GTA algorithm is able to narrow down large and complex solution spaces, and solve large instances of ATSPs to optimality, with runtime approaching a near-constant upper bound, implying that the primary bottleneck for GTA is no longer computational time, but rather hardware limitations: system RAM. The GTA framework is completely open and adaptable and can be quickly modified to adapt to other TSP variants and various combinatorial optimization problems.

We provide the source code and all its variants, with step-by-step clear and simple instructions, for deploying GTA and replicating its performance. GTA can be deployed and its code executed in a matter of minutes on any standard computer, without advanced programming skills. We are committed to transparency and are eager to share detailed codes and further experimental data, providing a foundation for future work.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files].

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

WN wrote the paper and developed primary coding, GAH supported further code development and manuscript editing. EAA and RA provided the needed academic credibility and have reviewed/edited the final manuscript.

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All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

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APPENDIX: Limited Benchmarks for ATSP Problems

Best Known Solutions For Asymmetric ATSPs

1. Reinelt, G. (1995) TSPLIB – A library of sample instances for the Traveling Salesman Problem. University of Heidelberg. <http://comopt.ifi.uni-heidelberg.de/software/TSPLIB95/ATSP.html>
2. Pedroso, J.P. and Kubo, M. (2010) Formulations for the Asymmetric Travelling Salesman Problem, OIL: Weekly Optimization Workshop, INESC Porto and Universidade do Porto, November 30th. <https://fc.up.pt/jpp/publications/asymmetric-tsp.pdf>

Unsolved Cases:

TSPLIB Instances	N	MTZ (Sec)	MTZ* (Sec)
td1000	1000	inf	inf
dc932	932	inf	inf
dc895	895	inf	inf
dc849	849	inf	inf
big702	702	inf	inf
dc563	563	inf	inf

Solved Cases:

TSPLIB Instances	N	MTZ (Sec)	MTZ* (Sec)	Z*
rbg	403	<i>137</i>	<i>116</i>	2465
rbg	323	<i>59</i>	<i>86</i>	1326
ftv	170	<i>>10MIN</i>	<i>175</i>	2755
ftv	100	<i>43</i>	<i>34</i>	1788
ftv	90	<i>47</i>	<i>10</i>	1579
ftv	70	<i>122</i>	<i>22</i>	1950
ft	53	<i>122</i>	<i>89</i>	6905
ftv	33	<i>2</i>	<i>2</i>	1286
MTZ*: MTZ Lifted Inequalities				

Best Known Solutions For Symmetric sTSPs

1. Reinelt, G. (1995) TSPLIB – A library of sample instances for the Traveling Salesman Problem. University of Heidelberg. <http://comopt.ifl.uni-heidelberg.de/software/TSPLIB95/STSP.html>
2. <https://www.math.uwaterloo.ca/tsp/concorde/benchmarks/bench99.html>
3. Pedroso, J.P. and Kubo, M. (2010) Formulations for the Asymmetric Travelling Salesman Problem, OIL: Weekly Optimization Workshop, INESC Porto and Universidade do Porto, November 30th. <https://fc.up.pt/jpp/publications/asymmetric-tsp.pdf>

Typical Runtimes Reported:

N	Runtimes (Sec)
2500	53738 ~ 15 hours
2000	14066 ~ 4 hours
1000	602
500	50
100	1

Large Cases Reported:

TSPLIB Instances	N	Runtimes (Sec)
rl11849	11849	~ 155 days
pla7397	7397	428996 ~ 5 days
rl5915	5915	2319672 ~27 days
fnl4461	4461	53420 ~ 14 hours
pcb3038	3038	80828 ~ 1 day
u2152	2152	45204 ~ 13 hours
rl1889	1889	10023 ~ 3 hours
vm1748	1748	2223 ~ 45 min

Medium-Sized Cases Reported:

TSPLIB Instances	N	Runtimes (Sec)
fl1400	1400	1548
nrw1379	1379	578
rl1323	1323	3742
rl1304	1304	189
d1291	1291	27393
pcb1173	1173	468
vm1084	1084	604
u1060	1060	571
si1032	1032	25
pr1002	1002	34
dsj1000	1000	410
rat783	783	37
u724	724	225
gr666	666	49
d657	657	260
p654	654	26
rat575	575	363
u574	574	23
pa561	561	246
ali535	535	53
si535	535	43
att532	532	109

Performance Comparison Against GTA:

Asymmetric Instances – ATSP

TSPLIB - ATSP INSTANCES			GTA - ATSP RESULTS				
N	MTZ (Sec)	Z*	Nodes (N)	GTA (Sec)	Z*	GTA (Scaled by Factor 10) (Sec)	Z* (Scaled)
			500	3	505	2.7	5044
403	137	2465	400	2	404	6.0	4043
323	59	1326	300	0.2	303		
170	>10MIN	2755	200	0.6	202	1.3	2052
100	43	1788	100	0.1	101	0.3	1076
90	47	1579	90	0.03	91		
70	122	1950	70	0.1	71		
53	122	6905	50	0.02	51		
33	2	1286	30	0.01	30		
			10	0.01	10		

Standard Symmetric Instances - sTSP

TSPLIB - sTSP INSTANCES		GTA - ATSP RESULTS	
N	sTSP (Sec)	N	GTA (Sec)
493	113.32	500	3
400	148.42	400	2
299	17.49	300	0.2
195	22.23	200	0.6
100	2.44	100	0.1
96	6.71	90	0.0
70	0.50	70	0.1
51	0.73	50	0.02
29	0.13	30	0.01
16	0.22	10	0.01